

The Impact of Blue Light Exposure from Screens on Circadian Rhythms

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Circadian rhythms encompass the physical, mental, and behavioral changes aligned with a 24-hour cycle, regulated by a circadian clock. This internal clock optimally coordinates biological processes, adapting to environmental shifts in light, temperature, and food availability, allowing *Homo sapiens* to optimize energy expenditure and internal physiology.

The regulation of sleep is intricately linked

to the circadian rhythm through the homeostatic physiology of the sleep/wake cycle, responding to environmental light changes. Blue light, part of the visible light spectrum (380 to 500 nm), primarily emitted by sources like LED screens, can affect our circadian rhythm.

While blue light exposure from screens is minimal compared to sunlight, prolonged screen time and proximity to the eyes can pose concerns. The eyes' limited ability to block blue light allows it to reach the retina, potentially damaging retinal cells over time and contributing to vision problems, cataracts, and eye conditions.

Notably, blue light exposure before bedtime disrupts sleep patterns by inhibiting

melatonin production, the hormone responsible for inducing drowsiness. This disruption affects the circadian rhythm, leading to sleep issues. Circadian rhythm disorders arise when an individual's internal clock misaligns with the external environment.

To enhance sleep quality, a practical approach involves minimizing exposure to disruptive blue light sources. Turning off such sources or using blue light filters and adjusting screen time before bedtime can help maintain a healthier circadian rhythm and improve sleep. It is also needed to have a sleep friendly environment.